

GOAL Project – Report of the publication analysis

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Project report regarding work package 2 of the GOAL project

Short abstract:

The GOAL project (Unlocking the Green Open Access Potential in scholarly and professional journals in Switzerland), which is funded by swissuniversities, aims to negotiate guidelines for secondary publications (Green Open Access Policies) with editors of practice-oriented journals. Such journals are a key publication medium for members of universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education. As a first step, an analysis of the publication output of the largest universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education in Switzerland for the years 2020-2021 was carried out. The aim was to find out in which journals they publish most frequently. The data set complements the results of the publication analysis already prepared and published in 2020 as part of the OA-EASI (Open Access for Educational and Applied Sciences) project.

This report describes the procedure of data collection for the years 20/21, their processing and the joint analysis of the data in the overall view from 2017-2021. A total of 5,925 journals can be found on the list, which will serve as the basis for the selection of candidates among the editors in the further course of the GOAL project. In general, the picture of a very diverse practice-oriented publication culture is confirmed. The publications are distributed among many small, practice-oriented journals published in different languages of Switzerland.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Contextualisation

The GOAL project (Unlocking the Green Open Access¹ potential in scholarly and professional journals in Switzerland) is based on the national OA strategy (2017) and the action plan developed in 2018 by Swissuniversities, the umbrella organisation of Swiss universities and academic institutions². The strategy aims to ensure that all publicly funded publications are made openly accessible by 2024.

An earlier project led by the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU), OA-EASI³, showed that researchers from universities of applied sciences (UAS) and universities of teacher education (UTE) publish most frequently in application-oriented journals from small publishers that are not covered by existing OA funding measures. Of the 1,232 journals surveyed for OA options in the OA-EASI project, 212 (17.2 %) are already Gold OA and slightly less than half (501 journals, 40.7 %) have a Green OA policy, but often do not use Creative Commons (CC) licences and protect articles with traditional copyright (13.5 %)⁴.

2.2 GOAL's Work Package 2

The aim of GOAL's Work Package 2 (WP2) was to supplement the data collected by the OA-EASI team with information for the years 2020 - 2021. Thanks to the updated data, a list of newspapers and journals should emerge in which members of UAS and UTE in Switzerland published most frequently in the period 2017 - 2021.

In order to obtain the data in a standardised form, a data form was sent to the institutions. Both types of higher education institutions (universities of applied sciences/universities of teacher education) from the different language regions (German-, French- and Italian-speaking Switzerland) received requests to share their publication data.

On this basis, it was possible to identify a list of journal publishers that do not have a policy for secondary publication (Green Open Access Policy) and may be willing to adopt one. Following Work Package 2 (this report), the team will contact key publishers to promote and negotiate (individual) Green Open Access Policies.

¹ By "green open access" we mean a secondary publication of a journal article from a toll access journal that is made freely available online on a disciplinary or institutional repository.

² <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/themen/digitalisierung/open-access/nationale-strategie-und-aktionsplan>

³ <https://oa-easi.ch/das-projekt/>

⁴ Rosenkranz, Simone, Andres, Valérie, Streitenberger, Martha, Stricker, Marius, Trautwein, Clemens, 2020. Analyse der Publikationen an Pädagogischen Hochschulen und Fachhochschulen der Schweiz 2017-2019. S. 10. Luzern / Muttenz / Zürich (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4458103).

3 Method

3.1 Data form for article publications

The first step was to define the mandatory and non-mandatory fields to be filled in by the institutions surveyed. The criteria were based on the publication analysis of OA-EASI, which made it possible to merge the collected data. Table 1 describes the data fields for the publication data collection:

Name_field_EN	requirement	type	description	examples
author	mandatory	txt	names of authors	
title	mandatory	txt	title of the publication	
subtitle	optional	txt	subtitle of the publication	
journal	mandatory	txt	name of Journal	
ISSN	optional	txt		
year	mandatory	number	year of publication	2018
publisher	optional	txt	name of Publisher	
location	optional	txt	publisher location	e.g. "Zürich"
affiliation_detail	optional	txt	name of organisational unit (Institute, Department)	eg. "Institut Energie am Bau"
ID_aff	optional	txt	original identifier in the database of the affiliation for backlink	e.g. "3f552ee9-9378-40ef-b1ab-0df64ee0e4d8"; "6386"
type_school	conditional mandatory if both types are in the data of the sender institution	categorical	educational or applied science	FH; PH
affiliation	optional (according to the sender institution)	txt	abbreviation name of institution	BFH; FHNW; HSLU; PHZH;...
publication_type	optional	txt	type of publication	publications in academic and popular journals and magazines; original research article, review, conference papers published proceedings, newspaper or magazine article

Table 1: Summary of mandatory and optional fields

3.2 Data handling (in R)

The data were mostly delivered in Excel or csv files and in the next step they were harmonised and prepared for import into R. The aim was to merge this data into one table. In this first step of data harmonisation, a qualitative pre-analysis of the supplied data was conducted before import into R. They were checked for compliance and adjusted according to the data collection of OA-EASI. This resulted in the GOAL dataset with article publications at UAS and UTE from the last 5 years (2017-2021)⁵.

3.3 Matching with data from the DOAJ portal (Directory of Open Access Journals)⁶ and with Open Access agreements⁷

The names of the journals based on the GOAL dataset were matched in DOAJ to identify Gold Open Access journals. The matching was done in R with a "merge" command by journal name with the current export of the journal list⁸ in DOAJ.

Existing Read&Publish agreements between journals published by Elsevier, Springer, Wiley, Cambridge, SAGE and Taylor&Francis and Swiss educational institutions, were matched with the GOAL data set in an analogous manner.

These data enrichments were used to identify which journals are already Gold Open Access or covered by a Read&Publish agreement.

3.4 Harmonisation of journal names.

Despite the high-quality data, the list of journals also had to be harmonised in terms of spelling, taking into account different languages. With the help of a command "Int_similarity" of the text analysis tool (quanteda⁹), journal names with slightly different spellings were marked and then manually saved under a harmonised name. Table 2 lists examples of such harmonisation steps.

⁵ In contrast to the publication data from the years 2017-2019, the publication types monographs, editorships and individual book contributions were not surveyed for the years 2020-2021.

⁶ <https://www.doaj.org/>

⁷ <https://consortium.ch/vertraege-konditionen/>

⁸ <https://doaj.org/docs/public-data-dump/> (abgerufen am 23.03.2022)

⁹ Benoit, Kenneth, Kohei Watanabe, Haiyan Wang, Paul Nulty, Adam Obeng, Stefan Müller, and Akitaka Matsuo. (2018) "[quanteda: An R package for the quantitative analysis of textual data](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00774)". *Journal of Open Source Software*. 3(30), 774. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00774>.

Table 2 Examples of unified names of journals

Notation 1	Harmonised Name
Frequenz: das Magazin des Fachbereichs Gesundheit	Frequenz
frequenz Das Magazin des Departements Gesundheit	
Les Cahiers Pédagogiques	Cahiers Pédagogiques (Les)
Cahiers Pédagogiques (Les)	
Leseforum	Forumlecture / leseforum / forumlettura - ch
Leseforum Schweiz. Literalität in Forschung und Praxis	
Leseforum.ch	
forumlecture.ch : littérature dans la recherche et la pratique / leseforum / forumlettura	
Forumlecture	

The harmonised journal names were assigned to the original article publication data and then a frequency analysis was carried out. Thus, a list of journals with the number of publications of all institutions and separately for the UAS and UTE is available as a basis for the selection of relevant publishers.

3.5 Open Access status of journals.

With the help of the collateral data from DOAJ and the Read&Publish Agreements, and with recourse to the open access status already determined in 2020 in OA-EASI, the journals with the most frequent publications were reassessed for their open access status in manual research work.

The journals were assigned into the categories that define their OA status:

- Gold (entire journal directly freely accessible under a CC licence)
- Green (Green Open Access Policy is published)
- Hybrid (individual freely accessible articles in an otherwise paid journal)
- Article freely accessible without CC licence
- No (no green policy)

4 Results

4.1 Update of the publication analysis

In the GOAL project, the data of 14 institutions were taken into account for the publication analysis for the years 2020-2021 - in the OA-EASI project, the data of 23 institutions were analysed for the years 2017-2019. In total, a data set with 16,045 publications was assembled, of which 8,890 had already been compiled in the OA-EASI project and 7,155 in the current GOAL project (Table 3).

Table 3: Overview of publication data for the analyses in the OA-EASI and GOAL project

Institution	Type	OA-EASI			GOAL		Total
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
BFH	FH	339	358	409	559	497	
FHGR	FH	41	56	64			
FHNW	FH und PH	365	343	230	250	201	
FHO	FH	142	138	130			
HEP-BEJUNE	PH	14	39	0			
HES-SO	FH	149	638	593	790	804	
HFH	PH	46	42	50	56	44	
HSLU	FH	382	376	334	352	391	
PHBE	PH	69	60	49	82	67	
PHFR	PH	35	21	21	20	9	
PHGR	PH	8	9	15			
PHLU	PH	56	52	40	63	59	
PHSG	PH	45	29	46	39	34	
PHSH	PH	9	3	9			
PHSZ	PH	35	31	32			
PHTG	PH	42	38	27			
PHVD	PH	101	99	97	144	134	
PHVS	PH	29	18	38			
PHZG	PH	38	28	25			
PHZH	PH	89	109	97	139	109	
SUPSI	FH und PH	195	197	192	135	109	
ZHAW	FH	0	800	625	1011	954	
ZHdK	FH	23	26	5	43	60	
Total		2252	3510	3128	3683	3472	Total
			8890		7155		16045

4.2 Journal analysis

Based on the harmonised journal names in the publication dataset, output of WP2 is a list of journals in which authors at UAS and UTE have published frequently during the period 2017 – 2021. This list¹⁰ is available on Zenodo in Excel and CSV format (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7046363>).

A total of 5,925 journals are on the list. The open access status has been determined or updated for about 300 journals with most publications. Candidates for the GOAL project are selected from these "top journals". These candidates are those in the categories "open access without CC licence", "green on individual request", as well as those that have not published a green open access policy (Table 4). That corresponds to a total of 289 candidates for negotiating such a policy within the GOAL project.

Table 4 Journal analysis by open access status

Open Access Status	Number of journals
Green	64
Green on individual request	10
freely accessible without CC licence	49
freely accessible without CC licence, after registration	2
freely accessible without CC licence, rights by the authors	1
Gold	62
Hybrid	6
No (no green policy)	93
no (older issues on e-periodica)	1
no (magazine discontinued?)	1
Overall result	289

5 Discussion

The update of the publication analysis from the OA-EASI project used data from 14 institutions. This means that fewer institutions provided data than in OA-EASI. Nevertheless, the number of evaluated publication records is comparably comprehensive in relation to the evaluated time period (on average 3577 per year for GOAL, 2963 records per year for OA-EASI), since it were primarily institutions with numerous publication records that provided data for the analysis.

Taking into account the language region and the type of university, the new data set, in combination with the OA-EASI data set, provides an overall representative picture of the publication activity of universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education in Switzerland. The lack of inclusion of some UTE and UAS is not very significant due to the low publication volume there.

The results confirm the findings from OA-EASI and show that the diversity in the publication culture is very high in both universities of applied sciences and universities of teacher education.

¹⁰ Corredera Nilsson, Enrique, Trautwein, Clemens, Andres, Valérie, Dobis, Dietrich, Flieg, Julia, Moritz, Andrea, Reymermier, Hélène, Rosenkranz, Simone, & Simukovic, Elena. (2022). Dataset underlying the Report of the Publication Analysis GOAL 2020-2021 [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7046364>

The number of publications in small journals in languages of the country is high. Many of these journals are often aimed at a non-academic specialist audience. Journals from large scholarly publishing houses with which publication agreements (Read&Publish) exist are of secondary importance in the volume of publications. None of the top 10 journals is covered by a read-and-publish agreement.

The review of the open access status of the top 300 journals shows that among the most frequently selected journals there are still 45 journals that publish their content freely on the web, but whose subsequent use is not possible without further legal clarification due to the lack of CC licences. It is obvious from the free access provided that the publisher's intention is to disseminate their journal content as widely as possible. However, the degree of dissemination would be served even more comprehensively if, on the basis of CC licences, it were clear to publishers and users, without further enquiry, how this content may be further processed and disseminated. To this end, it is advisable to publish a Green Open Access Policy on the publisher's website. With proactive advice from OA specialists, it is highly likely that publishers will consider the future use of a CC licence favourably.

The widespread use of CC licences is also likely to make sense for those 10 journals that already allow secondary publication on individual request. At the very least, it would reduce the effort required on the part of the publishers caused by repeated individual enquiries about the right of secondary publication. With a CC licence, the enquiries would be obsolete. The proportion of these journals might be higher than indicated here. Since this categorisation is based on the experience of the project participants, it is possible that in the course of the project, with the involvement of other stakeholders (e.g., the Sounding Board), journals that proceed in a similar way can be identified. Allowing secondary publication on a case-to-case basis signals openness to granting such rights to authors. They also offer an approach opportunity to negotiate the introduction of a Green OA policy.

The situation is less clear for the 93 journals (among the top 300) that currently do not allow secondary publication. In these cases, a comprehensive analysis of possible resistances, problems and needs on the part of the publishers will be necessary before and during negotiating a Green Open Access Policy.

6 Conclusion

The analysis lays a good basis for negotiations with the editors of these journals to achieve more OA secondary publications based on defined Green Open Access policies.

Success depends on the cooperation of the editors.